

ARASF

Atmospheric Research Airborne Support Facility

Flight Data Catalogue

Flight

A536

10 April 1997

OXICOA

FLIGHT FOLDER

Flight No. A 536

DATE: 10/04/97

Take off: 1015

Landing: 1510

Aircraft Scientist : KAYE
 Flight Leader : PERCIVAL
 Others : RICHER
 DEWEY
 HENT
 TIDDEMAN
 PICKERING
 PENNETT
 LAW
 GREEN
 BAUGALETTE
 MILLS
 BANDY
 GIDDINGS
 LANGRIDGE,
 BOYDE
 PURSE

Captain : FLT LT THORNHILL
 Co-pilot : SQN LDR O BRIEN
 Navigator : FLT LT CANNING
 Engineer : SGT LENNARDS
 Loadmaster : MENA QUICK
 FLTL PURSE
 FLTL MORRIS

Trials Instructions

ACSOE :

Operating area : SANTA MARIA → UK.

General synoptic situation

TIME: 12Z

POST FLIGHT REQUIREMENTS FORM

Flight No: 53.6

Date: 10.04.97

A/S Name: AKAYE

Aircraft Scientist's Post Flight Requirements:

1. Are any copies of the flight folder required?
YES NO for5.....

2. Flight data and folders will normally be discarded after 10 years, is this OK?
YES NO If not OK, state period

3. Is the flight part of an international project or major campaign?
YES NO Name of ProjectACSOE.....

4. Do you want the video tape kept?
YES NO How long?10 YRS.....

5. Has the Handheld camera or the Camcorder been used:
YES NO
If yes, do you want the handheld camera film processed:
immediately or when the film is finished?

6. Do you want the cloud physics data kept?
YES NO
If yes, which disc / file do you want it stored in?.....N/A.....

7. Do you want to do the interactive processing?
YES NO

NOTE:

- Members of MRF Radiation and Cloud Physics groups are expected to meet their own requirements for data storage and non-standard processing.
- For non MRF users, Data Management Section will keep the processed data TEMPORARILY until the requirements are made known.
- Any other requirements for post-flight processing and data storage should be discussed with the Data Management Section.
- If copies of the Flight Folder are required, it is the responsibility of the Aircraft Scientist / User to produce them.

OXICOA: Air Mass Characterization Transit

SORTIE OBJECTIVE:

To observe the atmospheric chemical composition transition ^{From} ~~from~~ Santa Maria to Boscombe Down. The data will be added to a systematically collected airmass data base. The data base will be used to determine the oxidising capacity and the budget of tropospheric oxidants in marine air at mid latitudes in the northern hemisphere.

Because of restrictions placed on the aircraft as a result of the rudder trim problem, there will be no special manoeuvres during the flight. The science will simply be making the most effective use of the transit.

LOCATION: North Atlantic Ocean

WEATHER: Cloud Free

FLIGHT PATTERN:

- [1] Depart Santa Maria, hold climb at 3000 ft for wet chemistry check.
- [2] Profile ascent FL170 at approximately 1000ft/min at 180 kts.
- [3] 15 minute run at FL170 for NO_x Calibration.
- [4] High speed transit to South West approaches at FL170, speed not critical.
Scientific measurements will be made during the transit, and bottles and bags will be filled.
- [5] 15 minute run at FL170 for NO_x Calibration.
- [6] Profile descent into Boscombe Down at approximately 1000 ft/min at 180 kts.

OTHER REQUIREMENTS:

Cabin pressure and temperature to be kept constant on level runs.

A536 10-APR-97

10:14:32-15:10:14GMT

INS TRACK - run no

AIRCRAFT SCIENTIST'S LOG

Project: ACSOE

Date: 10/4 1977

CPT A. THORNHILL

Aircraft Scientist: A. Kaye.

Flight No: A536

Page 1 of 4

GMT	Event Mark	Run No.	Height		INS	Omega		Other Info. (eg: clouds, weather, visibility, winds, sea state etc.)
			Pres/Rad	FL		Latitude	Longitude	
10:31:49	6	T.	3000	P	65	37.23 -24.95	in broken cloud layer. <u>LPAZ ←</u>	
10:36							cloud confounding on radar ahead crew asked to us to be prepared for some bumps.	
10:38								
10:42:16	7	XXXX P1	3000	P	49	37.54 -24.38	overcast small cu below and hazy.	
10:44							Starboard Sample pipe opened	
10:48:50		P1	100 150	F	46	37.79 -24.03	in cloud.	
10:54:46		P1	150	F	47	38.03 -23.43	still in cloud.	
10:57			165	F			still hazy but appears to be out of cloud.	
10:57:39		P1e/r	170	F	50	38.17 -23.54	still in cloud. Request climb to FL190 to get clear of cloud.	
11:06:16		R2	170	F	45	38.56 -22.96	just skimming bottom of clouds	
11:15:29	1	R2 R3	170	F	45	38.91 -22.49	2/8 sc below 7/8 ci above. HIGH SPEED TRANSIT	
							water-	
11:25:31		R3	170	F	47	39.65 -21.53	clear below some ^{thin} ci above high sc ahead above at the ground Some scattered clouds	

AIRCRAFT SCIENTIST'S LOG

Project: ACSOE

Date: 10/4/97

Aircraft Scientist: A. Kaye

Flight No: A536

Page 2 of 4

GMT	Event Mark	Run No.	Height		INS	Omega		Other Info. (eg: clouds, weather, visibility, winds, sea state etc.)
			Pres/Rad	FL		Latitude	Longitude	
11:29								FWD instrument has now settled down.
11:29								
11:33:50		R3	170	F	41	40.20 -20.71		Transition over front (?) line of small active cu, area behind clear, area ahead 8/8 sc. some ci above.
11:43:25		R3	170	F	41	40.69 -20.10		some < 1/8 ci above 8/8 sc below.
11:52:44		R3	170	F	47	41.28 -19.34		feathers of ci above ahead 8/8 sc below. Some a circular feature in sc ahead to left. general change from smooth cloud to rough with a north south delineation
11:55								drop in POT and increase in Humidity
12:08:02		R3	170	F	49	42.07 -18.21		haze layer above 8/8 sc below gaps gaps in sc ahead.
12:17:24		R3/P2	170	F	49	42.77 -17.24		haze above 8/8 sc below. climb to FL210 to get haze layer.
12:24:28		R2/R4	210	F	49	42.99 -16.95		8/8 sc below in haze layer sc clearing ahead.
12:31:21	12	R4	210	F	48	43.61 -16.08		clear below and above in a haze layer.
12:34:00	1B	P3	210	F	50	43.76 -15.07		

AIRCRAFT SCIENTIST'S LOG

Project: ACBOE

Date: 10/4/97

Aircraft Scientist: A. Kaye.

Flight No: A536

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GMT	Event Mark	Run No.	Height		INS	Omega		Other Info. (eg: clouds, weather, visibility, winds, sea state etc.)
			Pres/Rad	FL		Latitude	Longitude	
12:38:12	14	P3/R5	170	F	47	44.01	-15.51	streams of thin SE below clear above.
12:42:15	.	R5	170	F	54	44.30	-15.12	hazy clear above and below. SC ahead.
12:51:03		R5	170	F	50	44.79	-14.30	SE solid SC below and hazy, clear above.
13:02:00		R5	170	F	45	45.49	-13.39	SC below ending ahead clear above.
13:12:02		R5	170	R	49	46.15	-12.58	clear below and above.
13:24:14		R5	170	F	51	46.84	-11.49	hazy no cloud.
1340		R5						SHARP DROP IN WATER VAPOUR.
135807		R5	170	F	61	48.93	-8.33	HAZY, NO CLOUD. SEA VERY CALM.
141052		R5	170	F	57	49.57	-6.93	HAZY, NO CLOUD ABOVE OR BELOW. SEA VERY CALM.
141548		R5			57	49.79	-6.41	EXCELLENT VIEW OF THE SCILLY ISLES TO THE PORT OF THE AIRCRAFT.
1421:29		R5/R6	170	F	65	50.1	-5.7	NO CLOUD HAZY BUT GOOD VIEW OF SCILLY ISLES CORNWALL.
14:35:46		R6/P4	170	F	55	50.46	-4.44	VERY HAZY, NO CLOUD
14:40								Loss of All HORACE Screens.

12:10L

14:20

MISSION SCIENTIST'S LOG Project: OXICOA Date: 10/4/97

Mission Scientist: S. Penkett
K. Law

Flight No: A536 Page 1 of 3

GMT	Run No.	Notes:	
10:30	R1	FL030	<p>Low Sappov O_3 - uniform. Low NO_y - 200 pptv. → 150 pptv NO_2 Low H_2O_2 0.4 - 0.6 ppbv</p>
10:42-17	P1 ↑	FL030 → FL170 (no steps) 1000 ft min ⁻¹	<p>10:44 - sampling pipe for NO_y opened → t-of incorrect until low O_3 (→ 35 ppbv at 10:45) → Layer 10:47 → 10:50 (3-4 km) } <i>h-cl.</i> H_2O_2 ↑ 1.4 ppbv + inc O_3 } NO_y inc ↑</p>
11:00	R2	FL170	<p>Still in cloud - H_2O_2 dropped to 0.5 0.5 ppbv Just below cloud base out of cloud</p>
11:10			Calibration / zeros at beg. of R2 R2
11:13	R3	FL170	<p>Plot structure in mod H_2O_2 - correlatn directly with T_d - pr and cw C_n → StC_n ahead - frontal zone? - yes Much denser drop in T_d inc O_3, NO_y</p>
11:35	Passing through a front		<p>H_2O_2 NO inc O_3, NO_y H_2O_2 dropped 100-150 before NO - 60 pptv. NO_2 200-250 pptv. NO_y - 1200 pptv</p>
	Multi- correlatn (local Θ , T_d vs time)		
11:55	Change of air mass		<p>walter (Θ vs T_d) - lower O_3, NO_y, - very good correlation & higher O_3 and NO_y at 12:05 to 12:10</p>
12:05 → 12:10			
12:17-20	P2 ↑	FL170 → FL210 19.8	<p>Inc in O_3 → 80 ppbv. NO_y → 20 pptv inc 15-20 pptv NO. H_2O_2 drop at 12:19</p>
12:21-28	R4	FL210	
12:31-37	P3 ↓	FL210 → FL170	

MISSION SCIENTIST'S LOG

Project: OXICOA Date: 10/4/97

Mission Scientist: S. Penkett
K. Law

Flight No: A536 Page 2 of 3

GMT	Run No.	Notes:	
12:34:07	P3 ↓	FL 210 → 170	Haze layer - no cloud above or below. NO spike at 12:36 (also NO _y) NO _y reached
			actual start
12:35:12	R5	FL 170	NO below 10 pptv. O ₃ modelled H ₂ O ₂ > mean H ₂ C ₂ all the time Lower O ₃ , NO _y once past the Iberian peninsula (45°N, 15W)
13:00			Another layer NO up from ~10 → 15 pptv
13:05			Change of air mass (wetter)
13:09			NO _y 1 →
13:14			Passed out of cloud Clear above & below
13:15 → 13:20			NO _y 1 vs NO _y 2 - testing heating inlet → NO _y 1 - heating off at 13:08 → shifts ↓
			Layer at 13:15 NO _y up to 700 pptv, small inc in O ₃ No zero at 12:44? - not obvious in trace Spikes in NO up to 80 pptv - electronic noise? less PAN when high NO _y 8:1 NO _y : NO ₂ - less polluted 7:1 - plumes
	R6	FL 170 → ?	

Interactive Processing Log

Flight No. 536 Date: 10-04-97 User: KATE
Interactive by: PERCIVAL
Date: 17-04-97

Renav

KALMAN FILTERING USED

TWC

Profile plotted :

Line chosen : Profile / Whole flight / Other

a = -

b = +

c = +

NOT FITTED

LWC

OK

Heimann / Barnes

OK

Flight Leader's Pre/In-Flight Check List

CHEK
for auto selection

Flight No: 536 Date: 10 04 97

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GMT	PARA	NO	D.R.S.	DECODE	INSTRUMENT	EXPECTED VALUES	
						INFLIGHT	PREFLIGHT
0840	REF +	5	0567	✓			Approx 0568
	REF -	7	2854	✓			Approx 3071
	AOSS	19	4095	F/S O/S	TORQUE 3.5		2047 st. and level
	AOA	18	1339	F/S O/S	TORQUE 3.5		2047 st. and level
	RD HT	37	0000	✓			As Indicated 0000
	PR HT	8	3875	1005	1006		As Altimeter
	CABP	14	3298	1001	/		
	A/S	9	0083				As ASI 0000 - 0100
	UP1S	81	0203	19	18		
	UP2S	82	179	8	8		
	UIRS	83	0034		JNO2		
	UP1Z	84	152	✓			Approx 0147
	UP2Z	85	145	✓			Approx 0149
	UIRZ	86	0030		JNO2		Approx 2061
	UP1T	87	2555	12	15.6		As IAT
	UP2T	88	2574	13			As IAT
	UIRT	89	0000		JNO2		As IAT
	LP1S	91	0140	-3	-4		
	LP2S	92	0121	-8	-8		
	LIRS	93	2	-412	JNO2		
	LP1Z	94	150	✓			Approx 0150
	LP2Z	95	155	✓			Approx 0146
	LIRZ	96	002		JNO2		Approx 2050
	LP1T	97	2531	15	15.6		As IAT
	LP2T	98	2502	17			As IAT
	LIRT	99	0000		JNO2		As IAT
	J/W	42	0896	-0.1			As Indicated 0000
	NEPH	47	2888				
	HYGR	58	2888	14	14.5		
	HYCC	59	705	✓			696-901
	FDEW	138	4095				DP = (DRSU/20)-100 C
	FSTA	139	4095				
	DTF	10	4081	14	14.3		
	DTC	11	5		IAT - 15.6		
	NDTF	23	3774	15	14.6		same as De-Iced
	NDTC	24	5				
	INCT	48	2821				
	CCN	140	4095				less than 4095 if ON
	TWCD	70	4095				0000-4094
	TSAM	72	4095				0640-1860 < min
	O3	100	145				
	O3P	106	2034	960.6	✓		$P \approx (DRSU \times 0.4) + 145mB$
	O3RG	113	1684				
	MEIm	111	2630				
0800	PRTC	142	2378	✓			

Flight Leaders' Pre/In-Flight Check List

BCDS for auto selection

GMT	PARA.	NO.	H/D	D.R.S.	DECODE	INSTR	EXPECTED VALUE
0401	FL NO	1	Hex	0536	/		Flight No.
	GMTH	2	Hex	0090	/		Clock: First 4 No.s
	GMTM	3	Hex	0226	090226	/	Clock: Last 4 No.s
	E/M	4	Hex	003-5	✓		Event Mark Counter
	INCH	49	Dec				Multipxd Hkeeping
15.6 3425	1508 3255	3422	679	3422	3722	3426	131
	LATC	160	Dec	0000			Latitude
	LONC	161	Dec	0000			Longitude
0406							

Total Water Content Meter Check List

TOTW for auto selection

Height: NOT Fitted

GMT	PARA	NO	D.R.S.	DECODE	INSTRUMENT	EXPECTED VALUES	
						INFLIGHT	PREFLIGHT
	TWCD	70				0001-4095	
	TNOS	71				2000-3460 < min	
	TSAM	72				0640-1860 < min	
	TAMB	73				2400-3200	
	TSRC	74				2160-2470	
	HTR1	75				0000-4095 < 4095	
	HTR2	76				0000-4095 < 4095	
	ISRC	77				0001-1230 < min	
	STAT	78				4095	
	EV1V	170					
	EV2V	171					
	NPWR	172					
	EVIC	173					
	EV2C	174					

BROAD BAND RADIOMETER FIT

(pre-Flight only)

	PARA NO	POSITION	DOME	COVERS	OBSCURERS
UPPER	81,84,87	Port	Clear	Off / On	Large / Small
	82,85,88	Stbd	Red		
	83,86,89	Centre	Silicon		
LOWER	91,94,97	Port	Clear	Off / On	3NOZ FOR SILICON.
	92,95,98	Stbd	Red		
	93,96,99	Centre	Silicon		

Flight Leader's Pre/In-Flight Check List

CHECK

for auto selection

Flight No: 4526

Date: 10 04 97

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GMT	PARA	NO	D.R.S	DECODE	INSTRUMENT	EXPECTED VALUES
1037	REF +	5	567	/		APPROX 0568
	REF -	7	4855	/		APPROX 3071
	AOSS	19	1691	F/S	TORQUE	2047 st. and level
	AOA	18	105	F/S	TORQUE	2047 st. and level
	RD HT	37	1015	F102		As Indicated 0000
	PR HT	8	3178	6.2	F1065	As Altimeter
	CABP	14	3223	080		A/S
	A/S	9	1257	178		As ASI 0000 - 0100
	UP1S	81	0711	199	480	
	UP2S	82	1105	280	200	
	UIRS	83	0733	502		
	UP1Z	84	154	/		APPROX 0147
	UP2Z	85	152	/		APPROX 0149
	UIRZ	86	557	/	502	APPROX 2061
	UP1T	87	2929	2	-2.2	As IAT
	UP2T	88	2843	1		As IAT
	UIRT	89	022		502	As IAT
	LP1S	91	396	100	93	As IAT
	LP2S	92	189	12	-1	As IAT
	LIRS	93	179		502	
	LP1Z	94	150	/		APPROX 0150
	LP2Z	95	158	/		APPROX 0146
	LIRZ	96	352		502	APPROX 2050
	LP1T	97	301	-6		As IAT
	LP2T	98	2948	-5	-3	As IAT
	LIRT	99	022		502	As IAT
	J/W	42	1023	-0.1	-0.05	As Indicated 0000
	NEPH	47				
	HGR	58	1956			
	HYCC	59	739	/		696-901
	FDEW	138	1643	-17.8	/	DP = (DRSU/20)-100 C
	FSTA	139	977			
	DTE	10	3689	-3	-14.4	
	DTC	11	4			
	NDTC	24	4		-15.1	
	INCT	48	2605		-0.3	
	CCN	140				less than 4095 if ON
	TWCD	70	4045			0000-4094
	TSAM	72	4045			0640-1860 > min
	O3	100	0117			
	O3P	108	1585	779	/	P = (DRSU x 0.4) + 145mB
	O3RG	113	2084			
	HEIM	141	2471			
	PRTC	142	2378	/		

Flight Leaders' Pre/In-Flight Check List

BCDS for auto selection

GMT	PARA.	NO.	H/D	D.R.S.	DECODE	INSTR	EXPECTED VALUE
	FL NO	1	Hex	0536	4536		Flight No.
	GMTH	2	Hex	0113			Clock: First 4 No.s
	GMTM	3	Hex	0734	113734	/	Clock: Last 4 No.s
	E/M	4	Hex	9	/		Event Mark Counter
	INCH	49	Dec				Multipxd Hkeeping
-7.5 2449	3855 1268	2449	1290	2443	3772	2443	0176
240	LATC	160	Dec	460	40.48N	/	Latitude
	LONC	161	Dec	3864	-19.86W	/	Longitude
1140							

Total Water Content Meter Check List

TOTW for auto selection

Height:

GMT	PARA	NO	D.R.S.	DECODE	INSTRUMENT	EXPECTED VALUES	
						INFLIGHT	PREFLIGHT
	TWCD	70				0001-4095	
	TNOS	71				2000-3460	< min
	TSAM	72				0640-1860	< min
	TAMB	73				2400-3200	
	TSRC	74				2160-2470	
	HTR1	75				0000-4095	< 4095
	HTR2	76				0000-4095	< 4095
	ISRC	77				0001-1230	< min
	STAT	78				4095	
	EV1V	170					
	EV2V	171					
	NPWR	172					
	EVIC	173					
	EV2C	174					

BROAD BAND RADIOMETER FIT

(pre-Flight only)

	PARA NO	POSITION	DOMES	COVERS	OBSCURERS
UPPER	81,84,87	Port	Clear	Off / On	Large/Small
	82,85,88	Stbd	Red		
	83,86,89	Centre	Silicon		
LOWER	91,94,97	Port	Clear	Off / On	
	92,95,98	Stbd	Red		
	93,96,99	Centre	Silicon		

Flight Leader's ~~Pre~~ In-Flight Check List

Mig
Mar 1000

CHEK
for auto selection

Flight No: A536 Date: 100497

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GMT	PARA	NO	D.R.S.	DECODE	INSTRUMENT	EXPECTED VALUES	
						INFLIGHT	PREFLIGHT
1208	REF +	5	0567	/		Approx 0568	
	REF -	7	2893	/		Approx 3071	
	AOSS	19	1931	/ F/S O/S	TORQUE	2047 st. and level	
	AOA	18	1551	/ F/S O/S	TORQUE	2047 st. and level	
	RD HT	37	4095			As Indicated 0000	
	PR HT	8	1893	18.7	FLIP9 /	As Altimeter	
	CABP	14	2554	770	/		
	A/S	9	1397	185	✓	As ASI 0000 - 0100	
	UP1S	81	2738	918	402		
	UP2S	82	2364	448	440		
1328	UIRS	83	0943	-210	JNO2		
	UP1Z	84	150	/		Approx 0147	
	UP2Z	85	143	/		Approx 0149	
	UIRZ	86	872	/	JNO2	Approx 2061	
	UP1T	87	2941	-4	-2.7	As IAT	
	UP2T	88	2958	-4		As IAT	
	UIRT	89	0000		JNO2	As IAT	
	LP1S	91	289	55	52		
	LP2S	92	162	2	2		
	LIRS	93	0294	152	JNO2		
	LP1Z	94	148	/		Approx 0150	
	LP2Z	95	155	/		Approx 0146	
	LIRZ	96	300	-352	JNO2	Approx 2050	
	LP1T	97	2953	-4	-2.7	As IAT	
	LP2T	98	2431	-3		As IAT	
	LIRT	99	0000		JNO2	As IAT	
	J/W	42	984	-0.1		As Indicated 0000	
	NEPH	47	XXXX				
	HYGR	58	1632	-26	-34		
	HYCC	59	812	/		696-901	
	FDEW	138	1286	-35	/	DP = (DRSU/20)-100 C	
	FSTA	139	993				
	DTF	10	3857	-3			
	DTC	11	4				
	NDTF	23	3565	-3		same as De-Iced	
	NDTC	24	4				
	INCT	48	2598				
	CCN	140	XXXX			less than 4095 if ON	
	TWCD	70	2342	4095		0000-4094	
	TSAM	72		4095		0640-1860 < min	
	O3	100	174				
	O3P	106	1668	804.2		$P \approx (DRSU \times 0.4) + 145mB$	
	O3RG	113	1887				
	HEIM	141	2392				
1401	PRIC	142	2378	/			

R2

FL
1 low 13m + 2 low 1000

Flight Leaders' Pre/In-Flight Check List

D 51157 N
001330 W

BCDS for auto selection

GMT	PARA.	NO.	H/D	D.R.S.	DECODE	INSTR	EXPECTED VALUE
1402	FL NO	1	Hex	0536	A536	/	Flight No.
	GMTH	2	Hex	140		/	Clock: First 4 No.s
	GMTM	3	Hex	0353	140353	/	Clock: Last 4 No.s
	E/M	4	Hex	0014	14 /		Event Mark Counter
	INCH	49	Dec				Multipxd Hkeeping
-9.6 2416	1268 / 3850 /	2425	1313	2414	3768	2417	170 /
	LATC	160	Dec	0560	49	/	Latitude
	LONC	161	Dec	4011	8.		Longitude
1408							

Total Water Content Meter Check List

TOTW for auto selection

Height:

GMT	PARA	NO	D.R.S.	DECODE	INSTRUMENT	EXPECTED VALUES	
						INFLIGHT	PREFLIGHT
	TWCD	70				0001-4095	
	TNOS	71				2000-3460	< min
	TSAM	72				0640-1860	< min
	TAMB	73				2400-3200	
	TSRC	74				2160-2470	
	HTR1	75				0000-4095	< 4095
	HTR2	76				0000-4095	< 4095
	ISRC	77				0001-1230	< min
	STAT	78				4095	
	EV1V	170					
	EV2V	171					
	NPWR	172					
	EVIC	173					
	EV2C	174					

BROAD BAND RADIOMETER FIT

(pre-Flight only)

	PARA NO	POSITION	DOME	COVERS	OBSCURERS
UPPER	81,84,87	Port	Clear	Off / On	Large/Small
	82,85,88	Stbd	Red		
	83,86,89	Centre	Silicon		
LOWER	91,94,97	Port	Clear	Off / On	
	92,95,98	Stbd	Red		
	93,96,99	Centre	Silicon		

001

Flight Leader's In-Flight Log

10/100

Flight No A 536.....

Date ...10-04-97.....

Page ...1 of 1.....

Video Tape
No. A536 #1
Ends 1305
VIDEO TAPE FAILED.
(FFC) / DFC / RFC

	GPS	INU
Lat	36°58.28N	36°58.30N
Long	025°09.85W	025°09.85W
Time	083206	083242
Status	OK	GLLHWN

DRS recording to HORACE	(y/n)
HORACE recording to disc	(y/n)
SATCOM sending pos. reports	(y/n)

GMT	EVM	Height	QNH	Hdg	IAS	TAT	DP	DI Htr	Wind/Sea st.
81027				DATA	ON				
95040				SET	INU	TU NAV			
11432				Tape	OFF	SANTA MARIA.			
				Under course		pebbles.			
				START	Run 1				
02554	6	3000	1008	030	185	9.0	8.7	OFF	149/01
				END	Run 1	/START	P1		1000 FPM
24212	7	3000	1008	060	180	8.6	7.7	OFF	152/7
				END	P1	/START	R2		
5739	8	FL170	1013	060	190	-14.5	-15.8	OFF	227/7
				END	R2	/START	Run 3		
1324	9	FL170	1013	060	195	-13.9	-17.4	OFF	214/7
				END	R3	/START	P2		
				Accelerating to		Transit speed.			1000/m
1724	10	FL170	1013	060	240	-16.8	-21.4	OFF	170/16
				END	P2	//START	R4		
2120	11	FL210	1013	060	180	-25.6	-39.1	OFF	181/8
				END	Run 4	//START	P3		
3127	12	FL210	1013	060	230	-25.0	-37.4	OFF	160/9
				END	START	P3			
13407	13	F210	1013	060	230	-25.2	-35.8	OFF	162/9

Video Tape

No. A5364#2
Ends 1540¹³¹⁰

FFC / DFC / RFC

2 290/4 " 1017 +20

	GPS	INU
Lat	44°16.03 N	44°19.28 N
Long	15°09.01 W	15°03.11 W
Time	124223	124315
Status	OK	NAV

DRS recording to HORACE y/n

HORACE recording to disc y/n

SATCOM sending pos reports y/n

(25)

GMT	EVM	Height	QNH	Hdg	IAS	TAT	DP	DI Htr	Wind/ Sea st.	
				END	P3	//START RUNS.				
23912	14	FL170	1013	060	205	-16.5	-23.7	OFF	165/13	
				Descent	@	1420				
				END	RUN 5					
1420 via		FL170	1013	060	250	-15.7	-27.6	OFF	114/1	
"				START	RUN 6.					
142129	15	FL170	1013	070	120	-15.8	-26.9	OFF	062/1	
				END	RUN 6 / START P4					
143547	16	FL170	1013	060	180	-15.8	-32.1	OFF	276/1	
			INT	END	P4					
144045	17	FL100	1013	060	180	0-1	-41.2	OFF	327/2	
				Restart	P4					
144344	18	FL100	1013	045	185	1-0	-41.0	OFF	351/2	
				END	P4.					
15015	19	3000		070	210	11.7	2.2	OFF	227/2	
51014				LAND	BOSCAMBE					
				HOLD	AT	51°09.83 N				
						001°44.63 W				
				DATA	OFF					
				Power self failed. Tripped power.						

SAMPLE BOTTLE RECORD

Page 1

light no. AS36

Date 10/4/97

Sheet no. 1/2

Bottle no.	Time	e/m	Height	PRESSURE			True pressure (mb)	Remarks (Run no. etc.)
				Purge Time	Fill Time	End Time		
214	7.1		3000'	102840	103010	103101	914	
21	7.1		3000'	103633	104235	104330		
227	7.1		6000'	104409	104443	104521		
220	7.0		8500'	104615	104744	104841		
42	6.3		13000'	104754	105135	105315		
49	5.2		16000'	105445	105626	105851		
7H01	6.3		FL170	101728	101930	102128	527	
85	6.7		FL170	103300	103702	103445	529	
211	6.5		FL170	10470	120748	121000	528	
242	5.3		FL210	122503	122650	122920	445	
216	6.3		FL170	131000	131300	131455	529	
226			FL210	135700	135900	142118	529	

BAG FILTERS Log

Flight No	A336
Date	
operator	SJS

Time Zulu	Bag No	Event	Height	Run	Comments
1250Z	93	level	2000		
1251	246	"	2000		
1252	249	"	3000		
1254	27	"	3000		
1254	1014	✓	4500		
1255	209	✓	5500		
1256	1011	✓	6500		
1257	202	✓	8000		
1258	208	✓	9000		
1259	201	✓	10000		
1259	248	✓	11000		
1259	244	✓	12000		
1259	126	✓	13000		
1259	1007	✓	14000		
1259	245	✓	15000		
1259	127	✓	16000		
1259	137	✓	17000		
1300	123	✓	17100		
1301	125	✓	17100		
1324	247	✓	17000		
1330	92	✓	17000		
1335	1003	✓	17000		
1340	194	✓	17000		

16

BAG Fillers Log	Flight No	Date	Operator
	A 536		8/8

Time	Bag No	Event	Height	Run	Comments
1150	192	→	17000'		All fines are ZUCU
1155	170	→	17000		
1200	251	→	17000		
1205	225	→	17000		
1210	99	→	17000		
1215	193	→	17000		
1220	165	→	17000		
1225	180	→	17000		
1230	104	↑	21000		
1240	543	→	17000		
1245	120	→	17000		
1250	1009	→	17000'		
1255	96	→	17000		
301	544	→	17000		
1305	289	→	17000		
1310	1019	→	17000		
1315	1004	→	17000		
1320	191	→	17000		
1325	100	→	17000		
1330	197	→	17000		
1335	196	→	17000		
1340	228	→	17000		
1345	1000	→	17000		
1350	190	→	17000		

W

BAG Fillers Log	Flight No	Date	Operator
	A536		SLG

Time ZULU	Bag No	Event	Height	Run	Comments
1355	1019	→	17000		All items ZULU
1400	1015	→	17000		(except the MATABELE)
1405	1012	→	17000		
1410 1410	168	→	17000		
1415	181	→	17000		
1420	224	→	17000		
1425	223	↘	18000		
1430	165	↘	17000		
1435	198	↘	17000		
1437	40	↘	14500		Start of descent
1439	206	↘	13000		
1440	166	↘	12000		
1441	95	↘	10500		
1442	174	↘	10000		
1443	227	→	10000		
1445	177	↘	9800		
1446	228	↘	8000		
1447	103	↘	6500		
1447	97	↘	5500		
1448	151	↘	4500		
1449	195	↘	3500		
1450	550	↘	3000		
1451	226	↘	3000		
1451	222	↘	3000		Run: (fill other down)

PAN GC Log

GC Sample record			Flight Number: A536					Operator: RICHER / KENT					Date: 10/4/97				
Sample No.	Time	Height	Channel 1					Channel 2				Channel 3				Comments	
			ST	SP	DT	DP	BT	ST	SP	DT	DP	ST	SP	DT	DP		
			Optimisation = 13					Optimisation = 14				Optimisation = 16				INJECT = 40 s.	
			Back Flush = 33.68					Back Flush = 36.43				Back Flush = 37.25					
			Flow rate = 30.62					Flow rate = 29.56 30.64				Flow rate = 30.94					
1	10354	3000ft	315.45	2688				317.65	2544				314.75	2382			CP = 990
2	104803	ca. 8000ft	315.65	2258	35.9	1245	20.0	318.25	2175	21.8	1160		315.45	2016	27.5	265	CP = 970. *
3	100818	FL170	315.15	1830	26.3	1054	20.0	319.15	1741	30.0	962		316.15	1597	27.9	1095	CP = 780
4	111903	FL170	316.05	1833				319.35	1740				316.65	1597			CP = 786. *
5	113000	PUMP			OFF												
6	113300	FL170	315.85	1834				314.25	1736				316.45	1593			CP = 781
7	113824	FL170	315.75	1830				319.15	1732				316.35	1588			
8	114413	FL170	315.65	1829				319.05	1728				316.75	1582			
9	114952	FL170	315.45	1827				318.55	1724				315.95	1582			
10	115555	FL170	315.35	1825				318.75	1720				315.35	1581			
11	120232	FL170	315.5	1823	26.0	1054	20.5										AUTO SPACER ON
12	120502	FL170						318.45	1716	29.5	965						APPROX 10 SHOW A FAULT
13	120732	FL170											315.25	1578	27.5	1097	ON CHANNEL 3 is affected by pressure change at this

* Pressure decrease notable down 10mbar * INCREASE in P nitride up to 800mb
 + Unable to take many samples due to slow change in C.P.
 Page 1 of 4

PAN GC Log

GC Sample record			Flight Number: <u>AS36</u>					Operator: <u>LICHER / KONT</u>					Date: <u>10/4/97</u>			
Sample No.	Time	Height	Channel 1					Channel 2				Channel 3				Comments
			Optimisation = <u>13</u>					Optimisation = <u>14</u>				Optimisation = <u>11</u>				
			Back Flush =					Back Flush =				Back Flush =				
			Flow rate =					Flow rate =				Flow rate =				
ST	SP	DT	DP	BT	ST	SP	DT	DP	ST	SP	DT	DP				
14	121017	FL170	315.35	1821											Man	
15	121141	FL170							318.05	1715					Man.	
16	122158	FL210	315.25	1686	35.7	1046	24.7		317.65	1581	29.8	9166	314.55	1439	27.4	1095
17	122824	FL210	315.25	1689					317.35	1583			314.15	1441		
18	124106	FL170	315.15	1850					316.75	1730			313.55	1593		
19	124702	FL470			35.1	1081	28.5				29.8	9977			27.6	1125
20	125209	FL170	315.15	1845					316.15	1720			312.95	1588		
21	125104	FL470	315													
22	130450	FL170	315.65	1845					315.65	1720			312.45	1589		
23	131048	FL170	315.15	1842					315.45	1719			312.35	1588		
24	131623	FL170	315.05	1844												
25	1316	FL170							315.25	1635						
26	1316	FL470											312.15	1442		

PAN GC Log

GC Sample record			Flight Number: <u>A536</u>					Operator: <u>RICHARD / KENT</u>					Date: <u>10/4/92</u>			
Sample No.	Time	Height	Channel 1					Channel 2				Channel 3				Comments
			Optimisation = <u>13</u>					Optimisation = <u>14</u>				Optimisation = <u>11</u>				
			Back Flush =					Back Flush =				Back Flush =				
			Flow rate =					Flow rate =				Flow rate =				
ST	SP	DT	DP	BT	ST	SP	DT	DP	ST	SP	DT	DP				
<u>27</u>	<u>132318</u>	<u>FL170</u>	<u>315.05</u>	<u>1845</u>												
<u>28</u>	<u>132503</u>	<u>FL170</u>	_____					<u>315.05</u>	<u>1722</u>							
<u>29</u>	<u>132622</u>	<u>FL170</u>	_____								<u>312.05</u>	<u>1592</u>				
<u>30</u>	<u>133207</u>	<u>FL170</u>	<u>315.05</u>	<u>1845</u>					<u>315.05</u>	<u>1724</u>	<u>311.95</u>	<u>1592</u>				
<u>31</u>	<u>1338</u>	<u>FL170</u>														
<u>32</u>	<u>1345</u>	<u>FL170</u>														
<u>33</u>	<u>1353</u>	<u>FL170</u>														
<u>34</u>	<u>1360</u>	<u>FL170</u>														
<u>35</u>	<u>1410</u>	<u>FL170</u>														
<u>36</u>	<u>1419</u>	<u>FL170</u>												<u>Slight P change - 12m Rb.</u>		
<u>37</u>	<u>1425</u>	<u>FL170</u>														
<u>38</u>	<u>143140</u>	<u>FL170</u>	<u>315.15</u>	<u>841</u>					_____					<u>EXPLICIT P CHANGE</u>		
<u>39</u>	<u>144205</u>	<u>FL170</u>	<u>315.05</u>	<u>2206</u>					_____							

FL100

PAN GC Log

GC Sample record			Flight Number: A536					Operator: RICHARD KENT					Date: 10/4/97			
Sample No.	Time	Height	Channel 1					Channel 2				Channel 3				Comments
			Optimisation = 13					Optimisation = 14				Optimisation = 11				
			Back Flush =					Back Flush =				Back Flush =				
			Flow rate =					Flow rate =				Flow rate =				
ST	SP	DT	DP	BT	ST	SP	DT	DP	ST	SP	DT	DP				
40	144205	?	315.05	2206												
41	144509	?				315.25	2151									
42	144647	?								312.31	2095					
43	144839	3300ft	315.05	2497												
44																

Instrument Log Sheet: 1/10

Flight No: 536

Date: 10/4/97

Page: 1 / 1

Campaign: Aerosol Transit

Operator(s): FB

Time (GMT)	Altitude	Run	Zero / Cal	Comments
06:10				Switch a instrument - OK check liquid level - OK
	gnd		Zero On	
06:41				Data reupload to flight 536 run 2
09:02:12			Zero off	
09:6:28	gnd		Zero On	longer tubes seen down just before zero
	gnd			Send to <u>536 Cal - del</u>
				H1A - 128 MV 610 Bro 235 H1B - 173 MV 40 Bro 234
09:15:22	gnd		Zero off	
09:19:47			Zero on	92249 150 sec 160 200 sec 0 gms
09:24:42			Zero off	93210 146 40
			Zero on	93248 184 0 gms
09:33:15			Zero on	0935:12 144 7 40 0936:30 142 0 gms
				Pin set as <u>536 Run 1</u> on logger Power down
10:01:40	gnd		Zero on	Re-Start instrument
10:06				Reset logger 536 Run 1
10:15:24	↑	3000'	Zero off	
10:25:53	3000'	SR 1	ER 1	clouds
10:35				limi Trade logger ... ??
10:42:12	↑	SR 1		Cloudy to 17000'

Instrument Log Sheet: U2C2

Flight No: S36

Date: 10/1/97

Page: 3 / 1

Campaign: Acad Transit Operator(s): JB

Time (GMT)	Altitude	Run	Zero / Cal	Comments
133410				1.33 L/min: New Rock
1350				Change in Eqm Palt Temp noticed
1401				Under major air lanes in flight
141640				off @ 141840
	17000	ER5 SR		
142020				Reduce Speed to 180 kts
142128		ER5		
142128		SR6		@ 180 kts 15 min
143546		ER6		15 minute addition run for NOxy box. Zero down from H2O2.
143546		SP4	*	17000' descending to 3100'
1440	12000'		*	
144144	10000'			Intending profile timing to new heading
144344				Restart profile for 3100'
145014	3100'	EP4		
145631			2000h	
				Landing

NOxy Instrument Pre-Flight Log Sheet

Flight No: A536

Date: 10/4/97

Page: 1 / 1

Campaign: ACSOE / A20RE

Operator(s): SB / TG

Time (GMT)	SEQ.	NO (cps)	NO2 (cps)	NOy 1 (cps)	NOy 2 (cps)	Comments
0652	O ₃ HV on	on	on	on	on	array startup complete
0654	O ₃ HV on	on	on	on	on	
0655		NO _y converters still heating @ ~433°C (#1) 386°C (#2)				
0722		NO _y #1 converter @ 600°C				
		NO _y #2 @ 590°C				
0731		NO _y #1 @ 600°C				
		NO _y #2 @ 596°C				
0830		NO _y converters set back to 300°C (setpt)				
0850		NO _y converters @ ~305°C				
0911	cal	—	12528	—	31220	sequenced (new) } NO ₂ } NO
	∅	—	1347	—	505	
	cal	44466	46900	—	34896	
	∅	444	1259	—	499	
<u>NB</u>	after NO ₂ cal ∅, still cal coming through (on top of ZA)					
0932	∅ on	—	—	—	541	on NO _y 2 only
0933	∅ off	—	—	—	—	—
0935	∅ on	—	—	701	—	on NO _y 1 only
0935	∅ off	—	—	—	—	
0948		"Gnd" ZA cyl. RT → swap to "A/C" ZA cyl.				
0952	O ₃ HV off	- preparing for shutdown for power changeover				
0959		Syst ready for power changeover				
1000		O ₃ HV turned on				
1004		syst / laptop restarted but flow control lost				
1010		Syst restarted successfully				
1012	ARTIF on					sequenced
+ / off time		≈ 10:15 (30)				
<u>NB</u> : CAN FLUSH IS ON FOR ARTIFACT BECAUSE DONE						
power take off - still ∅ fastened / heat 10:18						

Note: All times logged as GMT

Delivery Gases (Gnd-A/C) Change Over Time: 0948

Power Change Over Time: 0959

Can Flush On: 1013

NOxy Instrument In-Flight Log Sheet

Flight No: A536 Date: 10/4/97 Page: 1 / 3
 Campaign: ALSOE/AZORES Operator(s): SB / TB
 Take-Off Time: 10:12 Can Flush Off: 10:25

Note: Enter Sequence (SEQ.) as Calib, Zero, Artifact

Time (GMT)	Altitude	SEQ.	NO (cps)	NO2 (cps)	NOy 1 (cps)	NOy 2 (cps)	Comments	Run
102554	3000							SRI
1027	3000						NOxy on ambient air	
1029	3000						NOy1 inlet temp. controller set to PULSE (1) like inlet #2	
1031	3000	ZERO	391	1204	572	449	sequenced,	
1033	3000						VERY HOT (CABIN!) O3 tubes #1 @ 32°C O3 tubes #2 @ 36°C	
1038	3000						zero values fed in conversions for DRS - DRS output sequences started -	
1040	3000						NO2 ϕ cell temp @ 12.5 (still very hot in cabin)	
104212	3000 $\uparrow$							ERI SPI
1044	$\uparrow$						standard sampling pipe on	
1057	17000	ZERO	435	1095	616	609	sequenced	
1057	17000	NON						
105739	17000							ERI SR2
1059	17000?	CAL on					sequenced (new seq.)	
1101	17000						NO2 ϕ cell temp @ 13.3°C	
1103	17000	CAL	-	14883	-	33917	sequenced	} NO2
	17000	ϕ	-	1110	-	390		
1110	17000	CAL	42807	46245	-	36189		} NO
1111	17000	ϕ	422	1070	-	393		
							NOxy laptop lock 5 sec slow (from DRS clock)	
							NO display on ANKUS = 1200 Full scale $\leftrightarrow$ 1100 pptv	
							NO2 = 3100 FS $\leftrightarrow$ 500 pptv	
							NOy1 = 7500 FS $\leftrightarrow$ 1000 pptv	
							NOy2 auto	
11324	17000						A/C speedy up for transit to BD	ER2 SR3

-K2 @ 11.13

Note: All times logged as GMT

$$pptv = \frac{[raw\ cnts - \phi\ cnts]}{sensitivity} - \text{Offset}$$

NOxy Instrument In-Flight Log Sheet

Flight No: A536 Date: 10/4/97 Page: 213
 Campaign: ACSOE / A2062 Operator(s): SB/TG
 Take-Off Time: 10:12 Can Flush Off: N/A

Note: Enter Sequence (SEQ.) as Calib, Zero, Artifact

Time (GMT)	Altitude	SEQ.	NO (cps)	NO2 (cps)	NOy 1 (cps)	NOy 2 (cps)	Comments	Run
11:21	17000						new zero values fed in conversions for OLS	
11:34	17000						passing over stratocumulus layer -	
display NOy - (NO + NO2)								
11:43	17000	ZERO	1420	1155	707	417	sequenced	
11:45	17000							
12:09	17000	ZERO	345	1024	572	315	sequenced	
12:12	17000						zero values fed to OLS conversions seq.	
12:17	21000						EP2 SP2	
12:21	21000						EP2 SRB	
12:31	21000						EP3	
12:33	21000						writing for air traffic clearance for ↓	
12:34	21000						SP3	
12:38	17000						EP3 SRS	
12:44	17000	ZERO	38	1026	576	280	sequenced.	
12:47	17000						new zero values fed in conversions for OLS	
13:09	17000						NOy #1 inlet temp. control turned off to check effect of heated inlet.	
							TAT @ 19°C	
13:12	17000						inlet #1 temp. @ 7°C	
							NOy 1 cnts dropped by approx. 1900 cnts. i.e. ≠ signal to add	
13:18	17000						NOy 1 inlet heater on again (70°C)	
13:28	17000	ZERO	346	1032	551	277	sequenced.	
14:16	17000	ZERO	338	999	560	257	sequenced	
14:18	17000						zero values fed in OLS conversions	
14:21	17000						SR6	
14:22	17000	ATL					sequenced.	

Note: All times logged as GMT

Formaldehyde Instrument Log Sheet

Flight No: A 536 Date: 10/4/92 Page: 1 1 3
 Campaign: ACSOE - TRANS B.D. ^{AZONES →} Operator(s): Mills
 Air Sampling Rate: 1.50 Peristaltic Pump Speed: 3 (rpm)
 PMT Sensitivity: 30 Calib Factor: _____ (V to ppt) _____ drs Bits = 1V
 Approx Lag Time: 8 1/2 hrs. React Coil Temp: _____

Time (GMT)	Zero/Amb	Inst. Output (V)	Other Info/Remarks e.g. Altitude, lamp output, sampling rate changes etc.
062500	Z	0.70	inst. turned on
064900	A	0.76	lamp = 73%. startat pump
0714 -	A	0	Solutions.
0716 -	A	0.85	(lamp = 53%).
			Sampling Rate = 1.7 slm (same setting as altitude - before when it was 0.50)
091140	A	A-?	Partsch Asidlet P. Pump tube replaced - no excess Pumping before run at 15 rpm for ~10 mins to get stuff through. - Blockage somewhere ←
10:33:19	Z	0.96	doing zero @ 3000'
10:36 01	Z	0.56	
10:38 20	Z	0.50/1	- 0.63 on brass Pt
10:39 20	Z	0.60	- zero baseline is 1.2 PPM
10:41 21	Z	0.56	
10:42 12	Z	0.46	end R1 SPIT
10:43 20	-A	0.48	started sample
11:02 40	A	0.50	Possibly working ok now - Prev data - is invalid because no Flow problems. Reagent IN flow is uneven; often non-existent

Formaldehyde Instrument Log Sheet

 Flight No: A536

 Date: 10/6/17

 Page: 2 / 3

 Campaign: Acsoe Azores (transit to 80) Operator(s): Willsy

 Air Sampling Rate: ~0.78 Peristaltic Pump Speed: 200 (rpm)

 PMT Sensitivity: 20 Calib Factor: $\frac{1 \text{ mV} = 15 \text{ ppt}}{\text{V to ppt}}$ 419.5 drs Bits = 1V

 Approx Lag Time: 2 1/2 Min React Coil Temp: 87

Time (GMT)	Zero/Amb	Inst. Output (V)	Other Info/Remarks e.g. Altitude, lamp output, sampling rate changes etc.
11:47:10	A	0.56	reach coil = 87.5°C Flow = 0.78 SLM, lamp = 701
11:50:53	A	0.54	
11:51:47	A	0.53	Not consistent readings in flowing at 1.0 0.108 ml/min or flowing freely.
11:56:00	A		Sampled cabin air to see if inst. responds.
11:58:20	A		Ended cabin air sample.
12:01:45	A		debubbler prob corrected - next 2/3 min invalid.
12:03:00	A	1.20	- System works - Cabin Air sam
12:08:10	A	0.77	- low data for next 10 mins is overvalued because of air coming with cabin air from test sample.
12:10:30	A	0.59	debubbler at its ⁶⁵ limit
12:12:00	A	0.53	
12:15:10	A	0.53	- Some burst streaming in system - Almost certainly due to low p + sample rate.
12:17:51	A		Stopped flow to cell to help debubbler.
12:18:50			re operator override pump.
12:20:19	A	0.50	
12:28:05	A	0.51	Sample = 0.64 SLM, lamp = 700

Formaldehyde Instrument Log Sheet

Flight No: A536 Date: 10/14/97 Page: 3 / 13

Campaign: ACSOE (AZORES) Operator(s): MILLER

Air Sampling Rate: 0.64 Peristaltic Pump Speed: 3 (rpm)

PMT Sensitivity: 20 Calib Factor: _____ (V to ppt) _____ drs Bits = 1V

Approx Lag Time: _____ React Coil Temp: _____

Time (GMT)	Zero/Amb	Inst. Output (V)	Other Info/Remarks e.g. Altitude, lamp output, sampling rate changes etc.
12:30 30	A	0.53	lots of back flowing in de-bubbler
12:33 35	A	—	de-bubbler failed - lots bubbles → detection
12:36 29	A		- stopped flow through cell to reset reagent de-bubbler. - little backflow on reagent
12:35 00	A	0.49	
12:37 50	A	0.52	
12:40 55	A	0.47	- Prob. too low reagent flow into then read from valve.
12:49 16	A		Air bubble about to go through detector
12:51 54	A		closed off cell to reset de-bubbler - but not working
12:52 47	A	0.70	re-set connect pump. - didn't work
13:04 65	A	0.43	next 5-10 mins prob huge - lots back bubble. - U. low value means. But reagent not going in
13:15 20	A	0.48	
			Total breakdown of flows - All data from flight are unreliable, probably rubbish
			Sigden just down.

A536, 10th April, 1997
ACSOE
Santa Maria to Boscombe Down.

<u>Start time</u>	<u>End time</u>	<u>Event</u>	<u>Height(s)</u>	<u>Hdg</u>	<u>Comments</u>
101432					Take off from Santa Maria
102554	104212	R1	3000'	060°	
104212	105739	P1	3000' - FL170	060°	1000fpm
105739	111324	R2	FL170	060°	
111324	121724	R3	FL170	060°	240 kts IAS
121724	122128	P2	FL170- FL210	060°	1000fpm
122128	123127	R4	FL210	060°	230 kts IAS
123407	123812	P3	FL210- FL170	060°	1000fpm
123812	142000	R5	FL170	060°	
142129	143547	R6	FL170	065°	180 kts IAS
143547	145015	P4	FL170- 3000'	070°	1000fpm
151014					Land at Boscombe Down

FLIGHT LEADER'S INSTRUMENT STATUS REPORT

FLIGHT NO: 4536

DATE: 10 104 / 47

MRF

INSTRUMENT	FITTED	OPERATED	COMMENTS
NAVIGATION: GPS OMEGA INU RADALT	/ / / /		
THERMOMETERS: DI TEMP NDI TEMP ICTP HEIMANN HYGROMETERS: GEN. EASTERN TWC FWVS J/W EXP. PITOT HEAD: STATIC PRESS. PITOT PRESS. GUST VANES	/ / / / / / X / / / / / / /		
RADIOMETERS: UPPER CLEAR UPPER RED UPPER SILICON LOWER CLEAR LOWER RED LOWER SILICON MARSS SAFIRE DEIMOS ARIES	/ / NOZ / / NOZ X X X X		
CHEMISTRY: OZONE ECGC NOX	/ / / /		
OTHERS: CCN CLOUD PHYSICS CABIN PRESS NEPHELOMETER PSAP	X X X X X		

A536 10-APR-97 12:52:39 014 Ω 44.87 -14.18 RV P

HDG deg	SPR mb	PHGT kft	TAS knots	TAT C	DEW C	WIND deg m/s
48.	529.	16.9	310.	-17.0	-25.3	150/10

OZONE MR 57.06 NOXY NOY 385.35

A	B	C	D	E	F	G	H
SPECT	PARAS	FREQ	ZOOM		VIDEO	HELP	

A536 10-APR-97 11:50:36 009 Ω 41.15 -19.55 RV

HDG degT 47.	SPR mb 528.	PHGT kft 17.0	TAS knots 306.	TAT C -15.3	DEW C -40.4	WIND deg 272 / 4
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NOXY NC2 153.35 NOXY NO 43.32 R3

A	B	C	D	E	F	G	H
SELECT	PARAS	FREQ	700M			VTDF0	HELP

A536 10-APR-97 12:44:33 014 Ω 44.41 -14.96 RV P

HDG degT 54.	SPR mb 529.	PHGT kft 16.9	TAS knts 309.	TAT C -17.1	DEW C -22.9	WIND deg m/s 165/12
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OZONE MR 69.54 -202 MR 0.55
ppb ppb

A	B	C	D	E	F	G	H
SELECT	PARAS	FREQ	ZOOM			VIDEO	HELP

1.2
1.2
0.2
0.3
0.2
0.01

A536

10-APR-97

11:47:12

009

40.94

-19.82 AS P

HDD	SEA	DUCT	TRE	TST	DEM	WIND
deg	fe	fe	knots	C	C	deg / s
46.	528.	17.0	305.	-15.4	-39.6	250 / 5

GE DEM = -39.56 FE DEM = -41.65 R3

H	B	C	D	E	F	G	H
SELECT	PRG	PRG	ZOOM			VIDEO	HELP

A536 10-APR-97 13:21:21 014 Ω 46.74 -11.78 RV P

HDG deg	SPR m ^b	PHGT kft	TAS knots	TAT C	DEW C	WIND deg m/s
49.	529.	16.9	309.	-14.9	-29.6	149/14

NOXY NOY 455.92 NOXY NOY 333.32

A B C D E F G H

A536 10-APR-97 13:03:51 014 45.59 -13.26 FC P

HDG	SPR	PHGT	TAS	TAT	DEW	WIND
deg	mb	kt	knots	C	C	deg m/s
45.	529.	16.9	307.	-16.1	-22.5	147/14

H2O2 YR 0.42 GE DEWP -22.53

-5.00
-13.75
-22.50
-31.25
-40.00
-48.75
-57.50

A536 10-APR-97 12:24:12 011 -- 43.13 -16.77 AS P

TIME	SEE	HEIGHT	TEMP	DEW	WIND
49.	448.	20.9	296.	-25.2	-39.0
					167/10

NOT 311.32 F - 25.2 C -33.52

SELECT	PARAS	FREQ	U	E	F	VIDE	HELP

A536 10-APR-97 11:56:03 009 Ω 41.46 -19.08 RV P

HDG deg 46.	SPR mb 528.	PHGT kft 17.0	TAS knots 306.	TAT C -16.3	DEW C -33.8	WIND deg m/s 203/5
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R3

A	B	C	D	E	F	G	H
SELECT	PARAS	FREQ	ZOOM			VIDEO	HELP

A536 10-APR-97 11:48:30 009 -- 41.02 -19.72 AS P

528.	17.0	307.	-15.2	-40.5	264/5
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309.62 -- 33.00 -- 41.72 RS

11:50	11:55	12:00	12:05	12:10	12:15	12:20	
SELECT	PAGE	PPRO	COOM	E	F	VIDEO	HELP

A536 10-APR-97 11:33:45 009 -- 40.08 -20.86 FC P

HDS deg	SPR mb	PHST kts	TAS knots	TAT C	DEW C	WIND deg m/s
40.	527.	17.0	305.	-14.2	-16.3	286/ 8

RZ

NOXY NOY 306.95 OZONE MR 46.26
ppb

HDG deg	SPR mb	PHGT kft	TAS knts	TAT C	DEW C	WIND deg m/s
41.	527.	17.0	306.	-14.6	-36.9	289/6

R3

0000 0000 0000 0000 0000 0000 0000 0000

A	B	C	D	E	F	G	H
SELECT	PARAS	FREQ	ZOOM			VIDEO	HELP

A536

10-APR-97

11:42:54

009

40.65

-20.15 FC P

HDC deg T	SPR mb	FMGT kts	TAS knts	TAT C	DEW C	WIND deg m/s
43.	528.	17.0	303.	-15.5	-41.6	247 / 5

GE DEWP
C

-41.51

H2O2 MR
ppb

0.20

R3

A536 10-APR-97 11:44:21 009 -- 40.75 -20.04 AS P

40.	528.	17.0	304.	-15.4	-41.3	244 / 5
SEE	HEIGHT	TAKE	TAT	NEW	WIND	
deg	deg	cross	C	deg	m/s	

309.45 309.72

1150 1200 1250 1300 1350

SELECT	PARAS	FREQ	Q	S	F	H
			ZOOM		VIDEO	HELP

A536 10-APR-97 11:24:51 009 = 39.57 -21.63 FC P

HDC deg	SPR mb	FHGT kft	TAS knots	TAT C	DEW C	WIND deg m/s
43.	528.	17.0	306.	-14.8	-15.6	277 / 5

RZ

POT 310.16 H2O2 MR 0.70
K ppb

A536

10-APR-97

11:21:21

009 Ω

39.35

-21.91 RV P

HDG degT 43.	SPR mb 527.	PHGT kft 17.0	TAS knots 303.	TAT C -14.9	DEW C -14.6	WIND deg m/s 258/ 6
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FEES HGT 5179.22 m GEOME MR 10.73 PP6 MOD H202 2.20 PP6
 0.00 25.00 50.00 75.00 100.00 125.00

A SELECT	B CHEM.	C ZOOM	D	E	F	G VIDEO	H
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A536

10-APR-97

11:13:21

008

Ω

38.89

-22.52 RV P

HDG deg T 46.	SPR mb 527.	PHGT kft 17.0	TAS knots 237.	TAT C -15.2	DEW C -20.4	WIND deg m/s 226 / 6	
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FEES HGT 5178.34 m NO. OF NOE 18.28 NO. OF NOY 537.51
 0.00 100.00 200.00 300.00 400.00 500.00 10000.00

A SELECT	B CHEM	C ZOOM	D	E	F	G VIDEO	H
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A536 10-APR-97 11:17:51 009 Ω 39.14 -22.19 RV P

HDG deg T 43.	SPR mb 527.	PHGT kft 17.0	TAS knots 298.	TAT C -14.9	DEW C -15.9	WIND deg m/s 242/ 6	
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FPES HGT 5180.98 m 4302 MP 0.56 ppb MOD H2O2 1.27 ppb
 0.00 0.50 1.00 1.50 2.00 2.50

A SELECT	B CHEM	C ZOOM	D	E	F	G VIDEO	H
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A536 · 10-APR-97 11:16:12 009 -- 39.04 -22.32 FR F

HDT deg	SPR mb	PHGT kft	TAS knots	TAT C	DEW C	WIND deg m/s
44.	527.	17.0	288.	-15.0	-15.2	233/ 6

A	B	C	D	E	F	G	H
SELECT	PARAS	FREQ	ZOOM		VIDEO	HELP	

A536

10-APR-97

11:06:18

008 Ω

38.55

-22.98 RV P

HDG deg T 45.	SPR mb 528.	PHGT kft 17.0	TAS knots 230.	TAT C -14.0	DEW C -13.4	WIND deg m/s 215/9	
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PPES HGT 5176.27 m H2O2 MR 0.54 PP6 OZONE MR 47.42 PP6
 0.00 1.00 2.00 3.00 4.00 P1 5.00

A SELECT	B CHEM	C ZOOM	D	E	F	G VIDEO	H
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A536 10-APR-97 11:10:57 008 Ω 38.77 -22.68 RV P

HDG deg 46.	SPR mb 527.	PHGT kft 17.0	TAS knots 241.	TAT C -15.0	DEW C -22.3	WIND deg m/s 217/6
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FEES HGT 5181.67 m CEONE MP 53.29 PP6 NOV NOV 939.44 PI
 0.00 33.33 66.67 100.00 133.33 166.67 10000.00

A	B	C	D	E	F	G	H
SELECT	CHEM	ZOOM				VIDEO	

A536

10-APR-97

11:09:21

008 Ω

38.69

-22.78 RV P

HDG deg T 46.	SPR mb 527.	PHGT kft 17.0	TAS knots 244.	TAT C -15.1	DEW C -19.5	WIND deg m/s 214/ 7	
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A SELECT	B CHEM	C ZOOM	D	E	F	G VIDEO	H
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A536 10-APR-97 11:32:30 009 Ω 40.01 -20.97 RV P

HDG deg	SPR mb	PHGT kft	TAS knots	TAT C	DEW C	WIND deg m/s
39.	528.	17.0	304.	-14.5	-21.0	272 / 6

H2O2 MR 0.70 MOD H2O2 1.44 PIF → R2

A	B	C	D	E	F	G	H
SELECT	PARAS	FREQ	ZOOM		VIDEO	HELP	

A536 10-APR-97 11:31:21 009 39.94 -21.08 FC P

HDG deg	SPR mb	PHGT kft	TAS knts	TAT C	DEW C	WIND deg m/s
48.	528.	17.0	304.	-14.5	-18.1	283/ 8

H2O2 MR 0.62 MOD H2O2 1.90 R2
ppb ppb

A536 10-APR-97 12:42:39 014 44.29 -15.13 FC P

Hdg deg	SPR mb	PHGT kft	TAS knots	TAT C	DEW C	WIND deg m/s
54.	529.	16.9	309.	-16.8	-24.1	165/13

H2O2 MR 0.53 MOD H2O2 1.05
ppb pob

A536 10-APR-97 12:26:18 011 02 43.26 -16.59 FC P

HDG deg T	SPR mb	PHGT kft	TAS knots	TAT C	DEW C	WIND deg m/s
49.	448.	20.9	309.	-25.2	-37.3	173/9

A536

10-APR-97

12:28:54

011 Ω

43.41

-16.36 RV P

HDG degT 48.	SPR mb 449.	PHGT kft 20.9	TAS knots 313.	TAT C -25.0	DEW C -37.3	WIND deg m/s 163/ 9
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4202 MR

0.18

NOXY NO

23.65

0.00

1.25

100.00

1.00

80.00

0.75

60.00

0.50

40.00

0.25

20.00

0.00

0.00

A SELECT	B PARAS	C FREQ	D ZOOM	E	F	G VIDEO	H HELP
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A536 10-APR-97 12:19:09 010 42.86 -17.13 FC P

HDT deg	SPR mb	PHGT kts	TAS knts	TAT C	DEW C	WIND deg m/s
47.	489.	18.8	267.	-21.5	-25.0	165/11

H2O2 MR 0.50 MOD H2O2 0.93
ppb ppb

A536 10-APR-97 12:27:27 011 Ω 43.33 -16.49 RV P

HDG deg	SPR mb	PHGT kft	TAS knots	TAT C	DEW C	WIND deg m/s
48.	448.	20.9	311.	-25.1	-33.6	168/ 9

H202 MR 0.17 NOXY NO 27.39
 1.25

A	B	C	D	E	F	G	H
SELECT	PARAS	FREQ	ZOOM		VIDEO	HELP	

A536 10-APR-97 12:40:09 014 Ω 44.13 -15.34 RV P

HDG deg	SPR mb	PHGT kft	TAS knots	TAT C	DEW C	WIND deg m/s
47.	529.	16.9	315.	-16.7	-23.0	164/14

-202 MR 0.40 NOXY NO 3.43
 0.00 100.00
 0.25 80.00
 0.50 60.00
 0.75 40.00
 1.00 20.00
 1.25 0.00

A	B	C	D	E	F	G	H
SELECT	PARAS	FREQ	ZOOM		VIDEO	HELP	

A536 10-APR-97 13:07:03 014 Ω 45.81 -13.00 RY P

HDG degT	SPR mb	PHGT kft	TAS knots	TAT C	DEW C	WIND deg m/s
45.	529.	16.9	308.	-16.2	-23.5	151/13

H2O2 MR 0.58 MOD H2O2 0.83
ppb ppb

A	B	C	D	E	F	G	H
1120	1130	1140	1150	1160	1170	1180	1190

A536 10-APR-97 13:12:51 014 46.20 -12.52 FC P

HDI deg	SPR mb	PHGT kft	TAS knots	TAT C	DEW C	WIND deg m/s
48.	529.	16.9	310.	-15.8	-27.6	146/14

H2O2 MR

ppb

1.25

0.46

MOD H2O2

ppb

0.62

A536 10-APR-97 11:41:12 009 Ω 40.55 -20.29 RV P

HDG deg	SPR mb	PHGT kft	TAS knots	TAT C	DEW C	WIND deg m/s
41.	528.	17.0	305.	-15.4	-35.0	256/ 4

L3

OZONE MR 74.64 NOXY NOY 970.45

A	B	C	D	E	F	G	H
SELECT	PARAS	FREQ	ZOOM			VIDEO	HELP

A536 10-APR-97 11:53:30 009 Ω 41.31 -19.30 RV P

HDG degt 47.	SPR mb 528.	PHGT kft 17.0	TAS knots 306.	TAT C -15.6	DEW C -40.7	WIND deg m/s 238 / 4
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NOXY NO2 175.21 NOXY NO 42.60

RS

A	B	C	D	E	F	G	H
SELECT	PARAS	FREQ	ZOOM			VIDEO	HELP

A536 10-APR-97 11:45:33 009 Ω 40.83 -19.95 RV P

HDG deg	SPR mb	PHGT kft	TAS knots	TAT C	DEW C	WIND deg m/s
41.	528.	17.0	306.	-15.3	-40.2	245 / 4

OZONE MR 78.58 -202 MR 2.10
ppb ppb

A	B	C	D	E	F	G	H
SELECT	PARAS	FREQ	ZOOM			VIDEO	HELP

A536 10-APR-97 13:05:12 014 Ω 45.68 -13.15 RV P

HDG deg	SPR mb	PHGT kft	TAS knots	TAT C	DEW C	WIND deg m/s
46.	529.	16.9	308.	-16.4	-21.9	146/13

-202 VR 2.42 VCVV VC :2.53
 000
 000

A B C D E F G H
 SELECT PARAS FREQ ZOOM VIDEO HELP

A536 10-APR-97 13:45:09 014 Ω 48.17 -9.59 FC P

HDG deg	SPR m/s	PRGT kts	TAS knots	TAT C	DEW C	WIND deg m/s
47.	529.	16.9	309.	-14.4	-34.3	142/11

H2O2 MR 0.30 GE DEWP -34.27
 P P P 1.25

-13.7
 -13.1
 -13.5
 -13.0
 -11.2
 -13.6
 -10.0

A536 10-APR-97 13:41:57 014 -- 47.97 -9.88 AS P

51. 529. 16.9 310. -14.7 -30.1 147/12

3:2.22 3:33.33 3:33.12

13:15 13:22 13:25 13:32 13:35 13:42

Chart12

A536 ascent

?

Chart13

A535 desc

A536fig

A536

NAUTICAL MILES SCALE
 N Scale is 1:300,000,000 at 60°N

80	70	60	50	40	30
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ASXXEGRR MSLP ANALYSIS DT 0000 UTC 10 APR 1997

Polar Stereographic Projection. Standard Parallel 30°N. Original scale 1:10m

APR '97 05:49 FROM MET ITOPS BRACKNELL TO 4806

METEOROLOGICAL OFFICE FAX FILED

FS/FUXX EGRR

POL STER. PROJ. STAND PARALLEL 60°N

1997 and draw in the Shipping and Seafarers. MET. D. 159, Bristol
 MET. D. 159, Bristol
 MET. D. 159, Bristol
 MET. D. 159, Bristol

LIST OF FORMS USED ON FLIGHT

No. of forms	Form Title
<p style="text-align: center;">4 1 </p>	<p>Aircraft Scientist de-briefing sheet Aircraft Scientist log Aircraft Scientist post flight requirements sheet Interactive log</p>
<p style="text-align: center;">1 of 3 2 of 3 1 </p>	<p>Flight Leader pre-flight check form Flight Leader in-flight check form Flight Leader in-flight log Flight Leader Video tape log (photocopy original)</p>
<p style="text-align: center;">2 2 3 3</p>	<p>SAFIRE log <i>BOTTLE LOGS.</i> CCN log <i>BAK LOG</i> MARSS log <i>PANGC. TRACE</i> DEIMOS log <i>MISSION SCIENTISTS LOG.</i> Chemistry log</p>
<p style="text-align: center;">/</p>	<p>Particulate / Filter boom Operator's log 2DC / FSSP / Holography Operator's log Sonde Ejector's log Navigator's log Photographic log (photocopy original)</p>
<p style="text-align: center;">1 / / / /</p>	<p>Instrument status forms RTD prints Raw data plots Weather charts Satellite pictures GPS track</p>

TDTRAJ_A970410.TXT

From 12Z 5/ 4/1997 to 12Z 10/ 4/1997

Arrows every 24 hrs

A536 10-APR-97

P1 3000'-FL170(104212-105739) + P2 FL170-FL210(121724-122128)

A536 10-APR-97

P3 FL210-FL170(123407-123812) + P4 FL170-3000'(143547-145015)

A536 10-APR-97 P1 3000'-FL170 From 104212-105739 Plotted 19-Jun-1997 13:31

A536 10-APR-97 P1 3000'-FL170 From 104212-105739 Plotted 19-Jun-1997 13:31

A536 10-APR-97 P1 3000'-FL170 From 104212-105739 Plotted 6-Jun-1997 10:08

A536 10-APR-97 P1 3000'-FL170 From 104212-105739 Plotted 6-Jun-1997 10:08

A536 10-APR-97 R2 FL170 From 105739-111324 Plotted 19-Jun-1997 13:34

A536 10-APR-97 R2 FL170 From 105739 - 111324 Plotted 19-Jun-1997 13:34

A536 10-APR-97 R2 FL170 From 105739-111324 Plotted 6-Jun-1997 10:11

A536 10-APR-97 R2 FL170 From 105739-111324 Plotted 6-Jun-1997 10:12

STATIC PRESSURE (MB)

No of obs 946
 Mean 526.961
 Standard dev 0.287879
 Max value 528.391
 Min value 526.377

DEICED TRUE TEMP (DEG K)

No of obs 946
 Mean 258.688
 Standard dev 0.488093
 Max value 259.500
 Min value 257.849

DEW POINT (DEG K)

No of obs 946
 Mean 255.664
 Standard dev 3.55642
 Max value 261.854
 Min value 248.367

OZONE MIXING RATIO (PPB)

No of obs 946
 Mean 48.8050
 Standard dev 6.26178
 Max value 59.8764
 Min value 40.1590

JNO2 TOTAL (E-3/S)

No of obs 946
 Mean 9.81059
 Standard dev 3.88841
 Max value 49.4207
 Min value 5.75467

PEROXIDE (PPB)

No of obs 946
 Mean 0.424676
 Standard dev 0.185965
 Max value 0.824000
 Min value 0.000000

PRESSURE HEIGHT (METRES)

No of obs 946
 Mean 5185.15
 Standard dev 4.06752
 Max value 5193.40
 Min value 5164.96

CORRECTED LATITUDE (DEGREES)

No of obs 946
 Mean 38.5305
 Standard dev 0.214966
 Max value 38.9044
 Min value 38.1618

CORRECTED LONGITUDE (DEGREES)

No of obs 946
 Mean -23.0436
 Standard dev 0.298014
 Max value -22.5297
 Min value -23.5690

NORTHWARD WIND COMPT (M S-1)

No of obs 946
 Mean 5.84130
 Standard dev 1.23279
 Max value 7.97099
 Min value 2.63654

EASTWARD WIND COMPT (M S-1)

No of obs 946
 Mean 3.77436
 Standard dev 0.768928
 Max value 5.28887
 Min value 1.23340

VERTICAL WIND COMPT (M S-1)

No of obs 946
 Mean 0.173201
 Standard dev 0.318079
 Max value 1.33652
 Min value -0.853905

WIND SPEED (MS-1)

No of obs 946
 Mean 7.02278
 Standard dev 1.07569
 Max value 8.97275
 Min value 4.35476

WIND DIRECTION (DEG)

Mean 212.869

TRUE AIR SPEED (M S-1)

No of obs 946
 Mean 122.645
 Standard dev 3.49204
 Max value 128.973
 Min value 116.676

HEADING (DEG)

Mean 47.7130

A536 10-APR-97 R3 FL170 From 111324-121724 Plotted 19-Jun-1997 13:43

A536 10-APR-97 R3 FL170 From 111324-121724 Plotted 19-Jun-1997 13:43

A536 10-APR-97 R3 FL170 From 111324-121724 Plotted 6-Jun-1997 10:25

A536 10-APR-97 R3 FL170 From 111324-121724 Potted 6-Jun-1997 10:25

STATIC PRESSURE (MB)

No of obs 3841
 Mean 527.228
 Standard dev 0.167230
 Max value 527.603
 Min value 526.279

DEICED TRUE TEMP (DEG K)

No of obs 3841
 Mean 257.545
 Standard dev 0.894272
 Max value 259.073
 Min value 256.161

DEW POINT (DEG K)

No of obs 3841
 Mean 246.248
 Standard dev 9.26291
 Max value 258.944
 Min value 230.965

OZONE MIXING RATIO (PPB)

No of obs 3841
 Mean 62.9057
 Standard dev 10.9091
 Max value 86.3517
 Min value 42.7659

JNO2 TOTAL (E-3/S)

No of obs 3841
 Mean 16.9305
 Standard dev 3.56692
 Max value 51.4803
 Min value 8.38073

PEROXIDE (PPB)

No of obs 3841
 Mean 0.391931
 Standard dev 0.234499
 Max value 1.04800
 Min value 0.000000

PRESSURE HEIGHT (METRES)

No of obs 3841
 Mean 5181.37
 Standard dev 2.36346
 Max value 5194.78
 Min value 5176.08

CORRECTED LATITUDE (DEGREES)

No of obs 3841
 Mean 40.8259
 Standard dev 1.12368
 Max value 42.7771
 Min value 38.9044

CORRECTED LONGITUDE (DEGREES)

No of obs 3841
 Mean -19.9375
 Standard dev 1.52516
 Max value -17.2601
 Min value -22.5297

NORTHWARD WIND COMPT (M S-1)

No of obs 3841
 Mean 3.58117
 Standard dev 3.24290
 Max value 10.5536
 Min value -1.31068

EASTWARD WIND COMPT (M S-1)

No of obs 3841
 Mean 4.08778
 Standard dev 3.42639
 Max value 9.12884
 Min value -2.60322

VERTICAL WIND COMPT (M S-1)

No of obs 3841
 Mean 0.661717
 Standard dev 0.186457
 Max value 1.31656
 Min value -7.266998e-02

WIND SPEED (MS-1)

No of obs 3841
 Mean 7.00046
 Standard dev 1.66726
 Max value 10.7599
 Min value 4.22410

WIND DIRECTION (DEG)

Mean 228.779

TRUE AIR SPEED (M S-1)

No of obs 3841
 Mean 155.784
 Standard dev 4.73547
 Max value 158.827
 Min value 121.516

HEADING (DEG)

Mean 45.9299

A536 10-APR-97 P2 FL170-FL210 From 121724-122128 Plotted 19-Jun-1997 13:44

A536 10-APR-97 P2 FL170-FL210 From 121724-122128 Plotted 19-Jun-1997 13:44

A536 10-APR-97 P2 FL170-FL210 From 121724-122128 Plotted 6-Jun-1997 10:26

A536 10-APR-97 P2 FL170-FL210 From 121724-122128 Plotted 6-Jun-1997 10:26

A536 10-APR-97 R4 FL210 From 122128-123127 Plotted 19-Jun-1997 13:47

A536 10-APR-97 R4 FL210 From 122128-123127 Plotted 19-Jun-1997 13:47

A536 10-APR-97 R4 FL210 From 122128-123127 Plotted 6-Jun-1997 10:28

A536 10-APR-97 R4 FL210 From 122128-123127 Plotted 6-Jun-1997 10:28

STATIC PRESSURE (MB)

No of obs 600
 Mean 447.962
 Standard dev 0.205890
 Max value 448.767
 Min value 447.508

DEICED TRUE TEMP (DEG K)

No of obs 600
 Mean 247.849
 Standard dev 0.240718
 Max value 248.275
 Min value 247.245

DEW POINT (DEG K)

No of obs 600
 Mean 236.051
 Standard dev 1.70446
 Max value 239.637
 Min value 233.412

OZONE MIXING RATIO (PPB)

No of obs 600
 Mean 72.1573
 Standard dev 3.58048
 Max value 81.1591
 Min value 57.5123

JNO2 TOTAL (E-3/S)

No of obs 600
 Mean 14.5825
 Standard dev 1.40829
 Max value 16.3531
 Min value 12.8613

PEROXIDE (PPB)

No of obs 600
 Mean 0.196840
 Standard dev 8.087493e-02
 Max value 0.512000
 Min value 0.112000

PRESSURE HEIGHT (METRES)

No of obs 600
 Mean 6376.32
 Standard dev 3.31831
 Max value 6383.63
 Min value 6363.35

CORRECTED LATITUDE (DEGREES)

No of obs 600
 Mean 43.2814
 Standard dev 0.173309
 Max value 43.5854
 Min value 42.9950

CORRECTED LONGITUDE (DEGREES)

No of obs 600
 Mean -16.5542
 Standard dev 0.247505
 Max value -16.1213
 Min value -16.9668

NORTHWARD WIND COMPT (M S-1)

No of obs 600
 Mean 8.70089
 Standard dev 0.662925
 Max value 10.2852
 Min value 7.57615

EASTWARD WIND COMPT (M S-1)

No of obs 600
 Mean -1.67422
 Standard dev 0.873292
 Max value 0.246132
 Min value -3.74593

VERTICAL WIND COMPT (M S-1)

No of obs 600
 Mean 0.412967
 Standard dev 0.369350
 Max value 0.941719
 Min value -1.15186

WIND SPEED (MS-1)

No of obs 600
 Mean 8.89836
 Standard dev 0.727160
 Max value 10.6281
 Min value 7.57846

WIND DIRECTION (DEG)

Mean 169.108

TRUE AIR SPEED (M S-1)

No of obs 600
 Mean 153.913
 Standard dev 8.85056
 Max value 161.167
 Min value 127.030

HEADING (DEG)

Mean 46.2908

A536 10-APR-97 P3 FL210-FL170 From 123407-123812 Plotted 19-Jun-1997 13:49

A536 10-APR-97 P3 FL210-FL170 From 123407-123812 Plotted 19-Jun-1997 13:49

A536 10-APR-97 P3 FL210-FL170 From 123407-123812 Plotted 6-Jun-1997 10:29

A536 10-APR-97 P3 FL210-FL170 From 123407-123812 Plotted 6-Jun-1997 10:29

A536 10-APR-97 R5 FL170 From 123812-142000 Plotted 19-Jun-1997 14:03

A536 10-APR-97 R5 FL170 From 123812-142000 Plotted 19-Jun-1997 14:04

A536 10-APR-97 R5 FL170 From 123812-142000 Plotted 6-Jun-1997 10:52

A536 10-APR-97 R5 FL170 From 123812-142000 Plotted 6-Jun-1997 10:52

A536 10-APR-97 R5 FL170 From 123812-142000 Plotted 6-Jun-1997 10:52

STATIC PRESSURE (MB)

No of obs 6109
Mean 528.605
Standard dev 0.148012
Max value 529.382
Min value 526.953

DEICED TRUE TEMP (DEG K)

No of obs 6109
Mean 257.655
Standard dev 0.850866
Max value 258.994
Min value 255.973

DEW POINT (DEG K)

No of obs 6109
Mean 246.596
Standard dev 4.51367
Max value 257.477
Min value 238.357

OZONE MIXING RATIO (PPB)

No of obs 6109
Mean 62.0610
Standard dev 5.01164
Max value 74.1309
Min value 43.3101

JNO2 TOTAL (E-3/S)

No of obs 6109
Mean 13.0090
Standard dev 1.98881
Max value 50.1286
Min value 10.8342

PEROXIDE (PPB)

No of obs 6109
Mean 0.440189
Standard dev 0.132752
Max value 0.792000
Min value 7.999998e-03

PRESSURE HEIGHT (METRES)

No of obs 6109
Mean 5161.94
Standard dev 2.08641
Max value 5185.25
Min value 5151.00

CORRECTED LATITUDE (DEGREES)

No of obs 6109
Mean 47.1348
Standard dev 1.75846
Max value 49.9724
Min value 44.0162

CORRECTED LONGITUDE (DEGREES)

No of obs 6109
Mean -10.9197
Standard dev 2.72064
Max value -5.88842
Min value -15.5037

NORTHWARD WIND COMPT (M S-1)

No of obs 6109
Mean 10.2737
Standard dev 2.73471
Max value 14.3198
Min value 1.38354

EASTWARD WIND COMPT (M S-1)

No of obs 6109
Mean -4.61497
Standard dev 2.20437
Max value 1.59017
Min value -8.34966

VERTICAL WIND COMPT (M S-1)

No of obs 6109
Mean 0.726387
Standard dev 0.228233
Max value 2.13234
Min value 5.174255e-02

WIND SPEED (MS-1)

No of obs 6109
Mean 11.3783
Standard dev 3.11747
Max value 15.8952
Min value 1.43220

WIND DIRECTION (DEG)

Mean 155.810

TRUE AIR SPEED (M S-1)

No of obs 6109
Mean 158.533
Standard dev 1.42895
Max value 172.710
Min value 156.976

HEADING (DEG)

Mean 47.6843

A536 10-APR-97 R6 FL170 From 142129-143547 Plotted 19-Jun-1997 14:07

A536 10-APR-97 R6 FL170 From 142129-143547 Plotted 19-Jun-1997 14:07

A536 10-APR-97 R6 FL170 From 142129-143547 Plotted 6-Jun-1997 10:55

A536 10-APR-97 R6 FL170 From 142129-143547 Plotted 6-Jun-1997 10:55

STATIC PRESSURE (MB)

No of obs 859
 Mean 528.363
 Standard dev 0.366810
 Max value 530.023
 Min value 527.823

DEICED TRUE TEMP (DEG K)

No of obs 859
 Mean 257.164
 Standard dev 0.160899
 Max value 257.520
 Min value 256.822

DEW POINT (DEG K)

No of obs 859
 Mean 242.782
 Standard dev 4.44349
 Max value 249.907
 Min value 232.456

OZONE MIXING RATIO (PPB)

No of obs 859
 Mean 65.3146
 Standard dev 3.61162
 Max value 74.4766
 Min value 58.2552

JNO2 TOTAL (E-3/S)

No of obs 859
 Mean 12.0276
 Standard dev 5.688650e-02
 Max value 12.1131
 Min value 11.2349

PEROXIDE (PPB)

No of obs 859
 Mean 0.420535
 Standard dev 0.109557
 Max value 0.792000
 Min value 0.192000

PRESSURE HEIGHT (METRES)

No of obs 859
 Mean 5165.35
 Standard dev 5.16920
 Max value 5172.98
 Min value 5141.97

CORRECTED LATITUDE (DEGREES)

No of obs 859
 Mean 50.2321
 Standard dev 0.123878
 Max value 50.4689
 Min value 50.0308

CORRECTED LONGITUDE (DEGREES)

No of obs 859
 Mean -5.08311
 Standard dev 0.375919
 Max value -4.44871
 Min value -5.73792

NORTHWARD WIND COMPT (M S-1)

No of obs 859
 Mean -0.826505
 Standard dev 0.628027
 Max value 0.620567
 Min value -2.00806

EASTWARD WIND COMPT (M S-1)

No of obs 859
 Mean 0.956997
 Standard dev 0.715284
 Max value 2.59032
 Min value -0.868721

VERTICAL WIND COMPT (M S-1)

No of obs 859
 Mean 0.201593
 Standard dev 0.251491
 Max value 0.704300
 Min value -0.379257

WIND SPEED (MS-1)

No of obs 859
 Mean 1.52102
 Standard dev 0.436674
 Max value 2.59058
 Min value 0.528036

WIND DIRECTION (DEG)

Mean 310.815

TRUE AIR SPEED (M S-1)

No of obs 859
 Mean 121.155
 Standard dev 0.583708
 Max value 122.179
 Min value 119.848

HEADING (DEG)

Mean 62.0786

A536 10-APR-97 P4 FL170-3000' From 143547-145015 Gelled 19-gun-1997 14:09

A536 10-APR-97 P4 FL170-3000' From 143547-145015 Plotted 19-Jun-1997 14:09

A536 10-APR-97 P4 FL170-3000' From 143547-145015 Plotted 6-Jun-1997 10:57

A536 10-APR-97 P4 FL170-3000' From 143547-145015 Plotted 6-Jun-1997 10:57

Glossary

Aircraft Position, Speed and Attitude

- **Navigation:** The aircraft carries GPS, OMEGA, and inertial navigation systems.
- **Pressure height:** is based on the standard atmosphere as specified by the International Civil Aviation Organisation (sea level pressure of 1013.25 hPa). Pressure height is quoted in terms of Flight Levels (height in hundreds of feet *e.g.* FL100 = 10000 feet).
- **Radar height:** altitude of the aircraft above surface, measured by radar.
- **Time:** All times are UTC.

General meteorology

- **Tephigrams:** are given for every major profile of each flight. A tephigram is a thermodynamic diagram (temperature (T) - entropy (ϕ) diagram) used to assess the static stability of a given atmospheric profile. Other meteorological organisations use similar diagrams such as the Emagram or the Skew T log p diagram.
- **Deiced true temperature:** air temperature with corrections for aircraft speed and altitude.
- **Potential temperature:** the temperature that a parcel of air would have if it follows a dry adiabatic lapse rate to the 1000 hPa level.
- **Dew point:** dew point (the temperature at which a sample of air would just become saturated with respect to a plane surface of water if cooled at a constant pressure) calculated from the chilled mirror General Eastern hygrometer.
- **FWVS Dew point:** dew point calculated by use of the Lyman- α spectroscopic instrument "the fluorescence water vapour sensor".

Cloud Physics

- **PCASP:** The Passive Cavity Aerosol Sampling Probe counts number concentrations (number per cm^3) of particles in 15 channels spaced pseudo-logarithmically over the diameter range 0.10 μm to 3.00 μm , to provide a particle size distribution over this range.
- **FSSP:** The Forward Scattering Spectrometer Probe is used to measure water droplets in the size range 0.5 to 47.0 μm diameter (cloud droplets). It has four range settings, each of which is divided into 15 size channels.

Chemistry Parameters

- **Ozone:** Calibrated readings from the TECO 49 ozone analyser in ppb. Instrument scientist: Joss Kent (UK Met. Office).
- **JNO₂:** The sum of upward and downward facing radiometers (raw data). Instrument scientists: Christoph Gerbig and Sandra Schmitgen (FZ Jülich).
- **Hydrogen peroxide:** Raw data recorded in ppb (approx.). Instrument scientist: Brian Bandy (UEA Norwich).
- **Organic peroxide:** Raw data recorded in ppb (approx.). Instrument scientist: Brian Bandy (UEA Norwich).
- **Modelled peroxide:** hydrogen peroxide concentrations as estimated from the concentrations of ozone and water vapour concentrations according to the following algorithm. The model is used in flight and is included in this data summary for individual scientists assessment of the use of algorithms for the purpose of in flight planning. Contact Brian Bandy, Claire Reeves (UEA, Norwich) or Dave Tiddeman (UK Met. Office) for details.

$$H_2O_2 = (k_3 j_4 [O_3] [H_2O]) / (k_5 [M] (j_6 + k_7 + [OH] k_8))$$

where k_3 is the rate coefficient for the reaction: $O(^1D) + H_2O \rightarrow 2OH$

k_5 is the rate coefficient for the reaction: $O(^1D) + M \rightarrow O(^3P) + M$

k_8 is the rate coefficient for the reaction: $OH + H_2O_2 \rightarrow H_2O + HO_2$

k_7 is the first order loss due to dry deposition. However, as the boundary layer is difficult to define, this term has been ignored for the time being.

j_4 is the rate coefficient for the reaction: $O_3 + h\nu \rightarrow O(^1D) + O_2$

j_6 is the rate coefficient for reaction: $H_2O_2 + h\nu \rightarrow OH + OH$

j_4 , j_6 and $[OH]$, calculated by a 2D model, are dependent upon latitude and time of year.

- **Formaldehyde:** Raw data recorded as bits. NB this instrument has a long time delay *ca.* 12 minutes. Instrument scientist: Graham Mills (UEA, Norwich).
- **NO_x:** Parameters (NO, NO₂, NO_{y1}, NO₂) were recorded on MRF's data recording system and are plotted in volts. Instrument scientist: Stephane Bauguitte (UEA, Norwich).
- **Bottles:** Please refer to the bottle flight logs (within the flight folder section to see when these were filled). Bottle filler: David Tiddeman (UK Met. Office).
- **Bags/CO analysis:** Please refer to the bottle flight logs (within the flight folder section to see when these were filled). Bottle filler: David Tiddeman (UK Met. Office). Analysis was carried out at ITE Edinburgh by Neil Cape. Plots of CO (ppb) with altitude (pressure height in metres) are included. Contamination has been noted in some of the bag samples, for further advice contact ITE Edinburgh.

ARASF

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